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ANALYSIS OF EQUITY CAPITAL EFFICIENCY IN FINANCIAL STATEMENT AUDIT

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Annotation: The essay highlights the challenges associated with assessing the enterprise's composition and reveals the economic substance and essence of its financial potential. In this context, an analysis was conducted on the factors influencing the change in turnover coefficients as well as the evaluation of the efficiency of private capital, including its profitability level. Based on the evaluation of the efficient use of private capital in the financial status audit, the scientific article's findings enable the assurance of the financial stability of businesses.

Key words: Long- and short-term liabilities, audit, balance sheet, financial capability, private capital, profitability, and turnover of private capital.

Introduction. The development of the free economy in our country, the wide-scale acceleration of mutual and international economic relations of business entities, undoubtedly, requires the demand for high-level auditing services. The audit system plays an important role in ensuring the financial stability of economic entities. At present, the development of national audit activities according to the requirements of the modern financial market, based on the requirements of the modern business world requires continuous improvement based on international standards. Today, economic entities in our country are financial status audit and analysis to do issues current is considered After all,our government by transition to international standards of financial reporting, auditing activities more development , economy host of subjects economic activity efficiency assessment , financial wellness system improvement regarding one how much decisions acceptance to be done [1,2,3,4] too economy in subjects financial condition audit transfer relevance and determining that it is of practical importance.

Assessment of the effectiveness of the financial potential of economic entities in the audit of the financial situation provides the main recommendations on their financial activity, management, and their solution to problematic questions. This, in turn, allows to improve the financial activity of the enterprise, to strengthen the calculation, to ensure the correct ratio of private and debt funds, to find and use internal opportunities, to ensure their future development and financial stability.

Analysis of literature on the topic . The issues of private capital efficiency analysis in economic entities have been widely studied in the scientific works of economists of our republic and foreign countries. In particular, A. Kh. Shoalimov, Sh. I. Ilkhamov [15], B. A. Khasanov [13], M. Yu. Rakhimov

[6], Sh. A. Tojiboeva [5,7,11], L. V.Dontsova [14], V.V.Tkachenko[10] considered the issues of financial potential analysis.

Tojiboeva Sh.A. The article published by [11] covers the main aspects of the analysis of indicators representing work activity. Based on the analysis of turnover indicators related to fixed and working capital and private capital and funds attracted from abroad, practical recommendations are given to ensure financial stability of enterprises. In particular, the methods of factor analysis of the efficiency of private capital of the enterprise were researched, and recommendations were developed to assess its impact on the financial situation.

The article "Assessment of the financial capabilities of Ukrainian companies and the possibility of forced liquidation" published by economists on this topic [9] discusses the issues of analyzing the efficiency of private capital in the assessment of financial potential. In world practice, there are many ways to assess the probability of bankruptcy of a company. At the same time, there are no methodological approaches to solving the question of whether a company can be liquidated in the event of bankruptcy. The article aims to assess the possibility of liquidation of the company in connection with the introduction of bankruptcy procedures and to develop a methodology for determining the financial potential of the company, taking into account the Ukrainian economy. It has been proven that the level of financial potential of a company is an inverse indicator of the probability of bankruptcy and liquidation of this company.

Economists Sivi Aryantini, Sapto Jumonolar [8], the purpose of the scientific article on "Firm profitability and value: the case of the manufacturing industry in Indonesia" is to determine profitability indicators and factors affecting them and their impact on firm value based on the DuPont analysis. Determinant profitability, i.e. net profit margin, total asset turnover and financial leverage multiplier have a positive effect on private equity profitability. In terms of contributing to firm value, private equity profitability has been shown to make a significant positive contribution to the industry. This requires the management to effectively manage the company's operational activities and reduce operating and other costs, increase the return on shareholder's capital and the profit margin, and use assets and liabilities effectively. In this article, these issues have been sufficiently explored.

The article published by Jo-Anne Sachard and Georg A. Shinkle [12] in the Australian Management Journal on the topic "Innovation in New Public Firms: The Impact of Government Grants, Venture Capital, and Private Capital" addresses this issue sufficiently. The article examines the influence of state grants, venture capital and private capital funds on the innovation of new state firms, input resources, innovative results (patents) and their quality (references to patents), the mechanism between state grants, venture capital, private capital and innovation. It shows that grants are incentives for private equity financing rather than direct investment. In addition, it is observed that the homogeneity of venture and private equity investors has a significant effect on innovation in portfolio companies at the firm level, and practical recommendations are provided.

Research methodology. The study was conducted in order to improve the practice of evaluating the efficiency of private capital in the audit of the financial competence of the enterprise, and based on the results, specific conclusions and proposals were presented. The scientific article uses the methods of comparison, horizontal, vertical and factor analysis. On the basis of these methods, the level and quality of private capital structure and efficiency, change, weight, and growth rate will be determined, and it will be possible to systematically control and comprehensively evaluate them. The correlation method was also used in the scientific article, and the correlation coefficient was determined based on the calculation of the functional relationship between the net income from the sale of products and the average annual value of private capital. The method of factor analysis is used to calculate each factor influencing the change of the private capital efficiency index.

Source: Compiled by the author .

Figure 1. Capital efficiency indicators

Financial audit important part from private capital s a m a r a li profit analysis. Private capital efficiency when you say , his effectiveness is understood . Private capital efficiency indicators in the system is expressed . To these x capital profitability , profitability and turnover input possible (Figure 1).

If accounting accounting and finance in the report x ususi from capital use in return removable income , profit or another result indicator to determine possible if , then this of indicators common volume not only that's it x ususi capital a belongs to part is determined . Such in the circumstances x ususi of capital real efficiency detection and analysis to do opportunity is born But for now such chance enough that it was not because of consequential indicators analysis will be done .

In the audit of the financial status of economic entities, the analysis of the profitability of private capital is one of the main indicators, and their financial stability is related to the correct formation of the profit received. Private capital profitability of the enterprise to himself belongs to has been of funds utility level characterizes . To calculate this indicator, we will make the following table (adval 3) .

The net income from the sale of products and the amount of private capital can be expressed by the following formula:

$$R_{xy} = \frac{\sum X \times Y}{\sqrt{\sum X^2 \times \sum Y^2}}$$

A correlation coefficient between 0.5 and 0.7 indicates a significant functional relationship. . Calculation results according to correlation the coefficient is 0.5 points organize did So , products from selling net proceeds received and private capital the distance between is average level functional is considered In the years of analysis in the enterprise, m a h solutions from selling 50 percent of the net income received private of capital to the size 50 percent of what q received while it depends on other factors .

Conclusions and suggestions. Estimating the financial potential is one of the main issues in ensuring the financial stability of enterprises and increasing efficiency indicators, and it should always be in the center of attention of the head of the enterprise, analysts and auditors.

Private capital is the basis of the company's own funds, and it is one of the important indicators describing the company's financial condition. Depending on its situation, the economic dependence or independence of the enterprise is assessed based on the composition of total funds. Therefore, " AVS " The turnover coefficients related to the equity capital of the joint stock company were analyzed, practical recommendations were given for the analysis of the factors affecting the turnover period, and the correlation between the net income from the sale of products and the value of private capital was calculated using the correlation method. At the same time, a method of analyzing the level of profitability of private capital was also recommended. So, the company is private efficient than capital to use as a result of the assessment, to establish their targeted management, to accelerate the circulation of money and liquid funds, and to ensure their financial stability practical it will be possible to set events . After all, the analysis of financial potential is important in determining the financial independence, stability, and creditworthiness of the enterprise.

The following practical recommendations can be made based on the results of this scientific article:

-in order to ensure the stability of the enterprise's financial potential, it is necessary to increase the amount of private capital and use it effectively. To increase private capital, first of all, it is necessary to increase the profit of the enterprise;

- Most of the expenses of the enterprises are the interest paid for the loan received from the banks and the cost of transportation. Due to this, the enterprise should increase the share of private capital in the working capital as much as possible and finally cover all the working capital at its own expense;

stability is to take measures not to increase the company's receivables and current creditor obligations. The large amount of liabilities leads to deterioration of the financial condition of the enterprise. Failure to meet payment obligations may lead to economic insolvency.

This is it recommendations the application of the audit in the practical activities of the enterprise allows to accurately diagnose their financial situation , increase the efficiency of private capital , ensure competitiveness, prevent bankruptcy, increase financial potential and ensure financial stability .

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